

Revisiting the Performance of Bundle-Recommendations: A Reproducibility Study of BRUCE

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In many business areas, a common marketing strategy is to not only offer individual products but also pre-defined collections of matching items, called ‘bundles’, e.g., music playlists of specific genres on audio streaming platforms. The task of bundle recommendation aims at suggesting bundles that match a user’s preferences. In the 2022s ACM Recommender System Conference, Brosh et al. presented “BRUCE: Bundle Recommendation Using Contextualized item Embeddings.” BRUCE is a Transformer-based bundle recommendation model which – according to the authors – significantly outperforms the current state of the art on three datasets (Steam, Youshu, NetEase). In this reproducibility study, we put BRUCE under scrutiny. In particular, we analyze the experimental setup to identify potential flaws and try to reproduce the reported results. Since we faced difficulties during the attempt of reproducing the results on Youshu and NetEase with our available hardware, we conduct only a subset of the original experiments. In particular, we found that the claims of the paper only partially hold when comparing BRUCE to two instead of four baselines on the Steam dataset.

1 INTRODUCTION

In “BRUCE: Bundle Recommendation Using Contextualized item Embeddings” [1] Brosh et al. present a novel bundle recommendation method based on a Transformer encoder [9] without positional embedding. The authors claim to achieve a significant improvement compared to the current state of the art. They evaluate different variants of their Deep Neural Network and also propose to initialize the weights of their model based on user-item representations learned from a Collaborative Filtering (CF) model (Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR) [7]). To avoid any ambiguity, we explicitly note at this point that BPR is also used as a baseline (see below).

For the evaluation, three different datasets are considered: (1) Steam [6], (2) Youshu¹ and (3) NetEase².

BRUCE is compared to the following baselines (incl. state of the art Deep Learning (DL) methods) on the above-mentioned datasets: (1) a Popularity-based Recommender (naïve baseline that recommends the most popular bundles, independently of any user preferences), (2) BPR [7] (CF method), (3) Deep Attentive Multi-Task model (DAM) [3] (DL-based method) and (4) Bundle Recommendation with Graph Convolutional Networks (BGCN) [2] (DL-based method).

The effectiveness of the methods is evaluated using the Recall@ k , the MAP@ k , the MRR@ k , and the NDCG@ k . Results are reported for $k \in \{5, 10, 20\}$ for all mentioned measures.

To determine whether BRUCE is significantly better than existing approaches, significance tests are conducted. In particular, they use the Friedman test as an omnibus test and Bonferroni-Dunn posthoc tests with a significance level $\alpha = 0.5$. The authors claim that the results achieved with BRUCE are statistically significant for *all* evaluated effectiveness measures.

Brosh et al. provide the source code of BRUCE and one baseline (BPR), and also the dataset splits used for training and evaluation, in a GitHub repository³. The code of another two baselines – DAM and BGCN – is also publicly available^{4 5}. However, the original code of DAM evaluates the effectiveness in a different fashion than BRUCE and BGCN do and the adapted code of this method is not provided by the authors. Furthermore, also the source code of the popularity-based

¹<https://www.yousuu.com/>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

²<https://music.163.com>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

³<https://github.com/tzoof/BRUCE>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

⁴<https://github.com/yliuSYSU/DAM>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

⁵<https://github.com/cjx0525/BGCN>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

recommender is not provided. All DL-based methods are implemented in PyTorch. Information on used hyperparameters for the Youshu and NetEase datasets – and how they were obtained – can be found in the papers or in the GitHub repositories. For the Steam dataset, only the hyperparameters used for BRUCE are reported.

This report is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) gives an overview of our used methodology and introduces our research questions. [Section 3](#) presents the most relevant key findings of the analysis of the experimental setup. [Section 4](#) and [Section 5](#) constitute the main contribution of this work and describe our conducted reproducibility experiments. Finally, we draw our conclusions in [Section 6](#).

2 METHODOLOGY & RESEARCH QUESTIONS

For this work, we use the following methodology:

- (1) We thoroughly review and analyze the paper and the additionally available artefacts and put the experimental setup under scrutiny.
- (2) We make an initial attempt to reproduce the reported results of BRUCE and all baselines on all datasets. This step allows us to narrow down further possible research directions since we also have to take into account that our available hardware might not be sufficient to reproduce all results.
- (3) Based on the outcome of (1) and (2), we further focus on the claims made in the paper and see if they also hold with a slightly adapted experimental setup.

As the methodology indicates, research questions are defined and answered in a step-wise manner. In particular, we reflect on the following questions:

RQ1a: *Which experiments can be re-evaluated using a commodity GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060)?*

RQ1b: *Do the reproduced results match with the reported ones?*

RQ2: *Do the claims of the paper still hold when BRUCE is only compared to a subset of baselines (BPR, BGCN) on Steam using Cross Validation (CV)?*

3 ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Based on a thorough analysis of the experimental setup, we present the following key findings:

- (1) From a technical perspective, the source code of BRUCE and BGCN ensures reproducibility to the most possible extent. All random states and seeds are set and PyTorch is restricted to use only deterministic algorithms. In contrast, neither for BPR (pre-training and baseline) nor for DAM random states and seeds are set.
- (2) As stated in the GitHub repository, the reported results of BRUCE on the Youshu and NetEase are achieved using multi-task learning. However, this detail is not mentioned in the paper.
- (3) In their original papers [3] [2], DAM and BGCN are only evaluated on Youshu and NetEase but not Steam. Brosh et al. do not make any explicit statement about whether hyperparameters of these methods were tuned on the Steam dataset nor do they report them. However, hyperparameter tuning is actually necessary to ensure a fair comparison.
- (4) As mentioned in [Section 1](#), the used omnibus test is the Friedman test and Bonferroni-Dunn tests are used as posthoc tests. A rationale for the decision on these particular tests is not given. Furthermore, ‘Bonferroni-Dunn test’ is sometimes used ambiguously in literature and they do not clarify which exact test they use. Often, it refers to *t*-tests with Bonferroni adjustment (which is what we assume), however, it may also refer to another statistical test that uses Bonferroni adjustment.

- (5) It is also not explicitly stated if the significance tests were conducted with results obtained *across* datasets or with repeated measures *within* datasets and no results across different runs (mean, standard deviation) are reported. In fact, testing across datasets may be considered bad practice in the given case since the achieved results across datasets are not commensurate [4]. Additionally, the authors do not clarify if all methods were tested against each other in a pairwise manner ('all vs all') or if BRUCE was used as a control method and tested against the baselines ('one vs all'). We further investigate this issue in [Section 4.1](#).

4 REPRODUCTION OF REPORTED RESULTS

The reproduction of reported results consists of three parts: (1) evaluate whether significance tests were possibly conducted across datasets, (2) an attempt to re-implement the missing baseline (popularity-based recommender) and (3) a re-evaluation of the experiments to determine which can be reproduced with our available hardware and whether the obtained results are similar to the reported ones.

4.1 Significance Tests

We use the reported results for the Recall@5, the MAP@5, the MRR@5 and the NDCG@5 with the same significance tests stated in the paper. We assume that BRUCE was used as control ('one vs all') and justify this decision since in the given case one should only be interested in whether the proposed algorithm shows higher effectiveness than the baselines. Using this test procedure, the null hypothesis of the omnibus test is rejected for all effectiveness measures. However, the null hypothesis for the posthoc tests is only rejected for the tests between BRUCE and the popularity-based recommender. Since the authors claim that their results were significant, we conclude that significance testing was rather done with repeated measurements within the datasets and these measurements were simply not reported.

4.2 Attempt of Re-Implementing the Popularity-based Recommender

We diligently tried to re-implement the missing baseline – the popularity-based recommender – to check if the results match with the reported ones. Unfortunately, our implementation yields results that highly differ from the reported ones (e.g., we obtain a Recall@5 of 0.5731 on Steam while a Recall@5 of 0.0012 was reported) and we were not able to determine the cause of this discrepancy. Hence, we do not incorporate this method in our analysis.

4.3 Re-Evaluation of Experiments

For the reproduction of the reported results (and also for all other experiments in this work), we only consider BPR, BGCN and BRUCE since the available source code of DAM uses a different evaluation scheme and we could not adapt it within reasonable time. Furthermore, we omit the evaluation of the MAP since the source code of BGCN does not offer a corresponding implementation. Initially, we faced some issues because the code of the considered methods crashed when running it as described. After applying the necessary bug fixes we also fixed the problem with the missing random state of BPR which was mentioned in [Section 3](#). Since the used hyperparameters for BPR are not reported, we use the number of latent factors that were used for the pre-training of the weights of BRUCE. To ensure a fair comparison, we tune the hyperparameters of BGCN on Steam. Details on the hyperparameter tuning and the used technical setup are given in [Section 5.1](#). [Table 1](#) shows, for a selected subset of the effectiveness measures, a comparison of the reported results to the ones we obtained. We can observe that the obtained results for BRUCE on Youshu are consistently worse than the reported ones. Our results of BGCN on Steam are better for the Recall@5 and MRR@5 but clearly worse for the NDCG@5. These deviations might be caused by certain assumptions we had to make for the hyperparameter tuning.

However, it is still difficult to tell if the reported results were achieved with hyperparameter tuning of BGCN or not. Due to insufficient GPU memory, we cannot reproduce the results of BGCN on Youshu with the intended batch size. Reproducing the results of NetEase on BRUCE and BGCN was also infeasible due to the large size of the dataset.

Table 1. Comparison of reported and reproduced results of BPR, BGCN and BRUCE on Steam and Youshu. Absolute deviations $>5\%$ are marked in bold

Method	Recall@5 [1]	Recall@5 (ours)	Diff. [%]	MRR@5 [1]	MRR@5 (ours)	Diff. [%]	NDCG@5 [1]	NDCG@5 (ours)	Diff. [%]
Steam									
BPR	0.4254	0.4376	2.87	0.3840	0.4341	13.05	0.3693	0.4075	10.34
BGCN	0.6078	0.6919	13.84	0.4735	0.5203	9.88	0.4886	0.4072	-16.66
BRUCE	0.8799	0.8765	-0.39	0.7065	0.7091	0.37	0.7343	0.7360	0.23
Youshu									
BPR	0.0764	0.0745	-2.49	0.0942	0.0942	0.00	0.0638	0.0634	-0.63
BGCN	0.0942	n/a [*]	n/a	0.1235	n/a [*]	n/a	0.0880	n/a [*]	n/a
BRUCE	0.1344	0.1285	-4.39	0.1465	0.1374	-6.21	0.1068	0.1001	-6.27

^{*} evaluation infeasible due to hardware constraints (insufficient GPU memory)

In summary, it can be said that re-evaluation on our available hardware only works on Steam (BPR, BGCN, BRUCE) and Youshu (BPR, BRUCE) but not on NetEase (**RQ1a**). Although the results do *not exactly* match with the reported ones and there are a few high deviations, they are also not completely unreasonable since we do not always know the exact hyperparameters that were used (**RQ1b**).

5 RE-EVALUATION OF STEAM USING CROSS VALIDATION

Based on the results presented in the previous section, we have to constrain our further analysis and suggest focusing only on the Steam dataset. In particular, we raise the question if BRUCE still yields statistically significant results when it is compared to only two baselines (BPR, BGCN) instead of four (**RQ2**). Due to lack of comparability, this may neither confirm nor refute the claims of the paper. However, we believe that our gained insights are, nevertheless, of relevance.

5.1 Experimental Setup

For our experiments we propose to use Cross Validation (CV)⁶, which might also provide more reliable estimate of the true effectiveness; the paper only reports results for a single train-validation-test split. In general, we try to adhere to the original as closely as possible.

Before splitting the dataset into folds, we randomly shuffle it. Since the original train-validation-test split has a 60-20-20 ratio, we use 5-fold CV. In each iteration, three folds are used for training, one fold is used for validation (needed for early stopping) and one for testing. The effectiveness is measured with the Recall@ k , MRR@ k and NDCG@ k ($k \in \{5, 10, 15\}$). Since it is computationally infeasible to re-run the hyperparameter search with CV, we use the hyperparameters obtained on the original dataset split. For BRUCE these are reported by the authors. The used hyperparameters for BGCN are unknown, hence, we tune them on the original Steam dataset split based on the Recall@5 to ensure consistency. The original hyperparameter grid of BGCN consists of 576 different configurations. We only consider a subset of 108 different configurations. The exact hyperparameters can be found in the BGCN config files in our provided code. For BPR we use again the number of latent vectors that were reported for the pre-training of the weights of BRUCE.

⁶We acknowledge that CV violates the independent assumptions of the statistical hypothesis tests but accept the introduced bias in exchange for ‘automatable decision-making’.

We also tried to follow the given experimental setup as closely as possible from a technical perspective. However, Brosh et al. did not include the versions of all used libraries and also the used Python version is unknown. Thus, we had to make certain assumptions. Although the used CUDA version is mentioned (10.2), this version is not supported by our GPU.

We run our experiments with the following system configuration:

- CPU: AMD Ryzen 5 5600X
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060
- PyTorch 1.13.1 (CUDA 11.6)
- Experiments are executed in Docker containers (base image: python:3.8-slim-buster; Docker 20.10.21)

The versions of all other used libraries can be found in the respective dependency files (requirements.txt files) in our provided source code.

For significance testing we use the same significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) and also the same posthoc test as stated in the paper. However, we use the Friedman Aligned Rank [5] test instead of the Friedman test as omnibus test since we have a lower number of groups compared to the original experimental setup. BRUCE is used as a control and tested against the other two methods. All significance tests are conducted on the STAC web platform⁷ [8].

5.2 Results and Discussion

The training process of the best found BGCN hyperparameter configuration⁸ is visualized in Figure 1. The best achieved Recall@5 on the validation set is 75.4%. Additionally, Figure 2 shows the training process of BRUCE using 5-fold CV. Based on the right subplot we can infer that results across folds are relatively consistent for this method.

Fig. 1. Training of the best hyperparameter configuration of BGCN on the original Steam dataset split. Left: error on the training set. Right: Recall on the validation set.

Table 2 shows aggregated results (mean and standard deviation) of the 5-fold CV. The detailed results per fold are given in Appendix A. We can make the following observations:

- (1) The reported results of the paper are within two standard deviations from the mean for all effectiveness measures except for the Recall@10, the Recall@20 and the NDGC (at all levels of k) for BGCN. In particular, the results of the NDCG of BGCN show particularly high deviations from the reported results, which could already be observed on the original dataset split (see Table 1). Unfortunately, we cannot provide a reliable rationale for this deviation but it may be caused by different hyperparameters.

⁷<https://tec.citius.usc.es/stac/index.html>, Accessed: 2023-01-15

⁸learning rate 0.001, L_2 regularization strength $1e-7$, message dropout 0.2, node dropout 0.3, no training with hard-negative samples

Fig. 2. Training of BRUCE using 5-fold CV with indicated confidence intervals. Left: error on the training set. Right: Recall on the validation set (the validation set is only evaluated from epoch 8200 onwards).

(2) BRUCE clearly provides more stable results across folds than the other two methods, i.e., BPR and BGCN are very sensitive to changes in the dataset split which is indicated by the higher standard deviations.

Based on the obtained results, the null hypothesis of the omnibus test (Friedman Aligned Ranks test) is rejected for all effectiveness measures. The subsequent posthoc tests show that there is only a significant difference between BRUCE and all other methods for the NDCG@5, NDCG@10 and NDCG@20. For the remaining effectiveness measures, the null hypothesis of the posthoc tests is only rejected for BRUCE vs BPR. Hence, for the Recall and MRR at all levels there is no significant difference in the performance of BRUCE and BGCN. Therefore, we can answer **RQ2** as follows: if BRUCE is only compared to a subset of two baselines, namely BPR and BGCN, on Steam, the claims of the paper do only partially hold. This is, BRUCE does not perform significantly better than *all* baselines on *all* effectiveness measures. We want to emphasize once more that our experiments *not refute* the claims made in the paper but state that the claims do not hold with our different experimental setup.

Table 2. Aggregated results (mean (\pm std)) of 5-fold CV on Steam. The best results are marked in bold

Method	Recall@5	Recall@10	Recall@20	MRR@5	MRR@10	MRR@20	NDCG@5	NDCG@10	NDCG@20
BPR	0.4104 (± 0.0420)	0.4533 (± 0.0072)	0.4864 (± 0.0071)	0.376 (± 0.0344)	0.3819 (± 0.0315)	0.3842 (± 0.0315)	0.3598 (± 0.0327)	0.3743 (± 0.0243)	0.3835 (± 0.0246)
BGCN	0.6411 (± 0.0186)	0.8298 (± 0.0112)	0.9193 (± 0.0049)	0.466 (± 0.0158)	0.4873 (± 0.0151)	0.4929 (± 0.0145)	0.3624 (± 0.0240)	0.3804 (± 0.0252)	0.3843 (± 0.0266)
BRUCE	0.8755 (± 0.0038)	0.9533 (± 0.0026)	0.9801 (± 0.0015) [*]	0.7101 (± 0.0042)	0.7180 (± 0.0042)	0.7195 (± 0.0039)	0.7365 (± 0.0040) [†]	0.7653 (± 0.0036) [†]	0.7732 (± 0.0031) [†]

^{*} BRUCE vs BPR significant

[†] BRUCE vs BGCN significant

6 CONCLUSION

This work presented a reproducibility study of “BRUCE: Bundle Recommendation Using Contextualized item Embeddings”. Beginning with an initial analysis of the experimental setup, we made an attempt to reproduce and verify the results reported in the paper. Unfortunately, we did not manage to implement the missing baseline and also could not adapt the code of DAM in a way that adheres to the evaluation of the other methods. Due to computational limitations, we restricted the main part of this reproducibility study to the Steam dataset and evaluated BRUCE and two baselines using 5-fold CV. We found that the results on the NDCG yielded particularly high deviations from the reported ones, however, we believe that this may be an effect of different hyperparameters. Furthermore, we noticed that the claims of the paper – a statistically significant improvement of BRUCE compared to all baselines – only partially held when conducting the significance tests solely against two instead of four baselines.

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A APPENDIX: DETAILED RESULTS OF 5-FOLD CV ON STEAM

Table 3. Results of 5-fold CV on Steam per fold. The best results are marked in bold

Method	Recall@5	Recall@10	Recall@20	MRR@5	MRR@10	MRR@20	NDCG@5	NDCG@10	NDCG@20
Fold 0									
BPR	0.4240	0.4514	0.4883	0.3682	0.3723	0.3749	0.3574	0.3673	0.3776
BGCN	0.6604	0.8394	0.9217	0.4766	0.4971	0.5022	0.3641	0.3726	0.3742
BRUCE	0.8768	0.9525	0.9809	0.7122	0.7198	0.7213	0.7387	0.7665	0.7748
Fold 1									
BPR	0.3366	0.4438	0.4743	0.3340	0.3475	0.3497	0.3119	0.3460	0.3545
BGCN	0.6497	0.8309	0.9157	0.4826	0.5030	0.5082	0.3920	0.4083	0.4132
BRUCE	0.8746	0.9547	0.9812	0.7111	0.7189	0.7192	0.7373	0.7664	0.7733
Fold 2									
BPR	0.4195	0.4503	0.4868	0.3775	0.3821	0.3847	0.3635	0.3745	0.3846
BGCN	0.6114	0.8135	0.9138	0.4426	0.4656	0.4721	0.3328	0.3425	0.3445
BRUCE	0.8718	0.9527	0.9796	0.7032	0.7116	0.7135	0.7304	0.7605	0.7688
Fold 3									
BPR	0.4385	0.4617	0.4903	0.3707	0.3742	0.3763	0.3620	0.3705	0.3785
BGCN	0.6365	0.8406	0.9261	0.4692	0.4923	0.4976	0.3781	0.3966	0.4016
BRUCE	0.8730	0.9498	0.9777	0.7100	0.7169	0.7197	0.7351	0.7632	0.7723
Fold 4									
BPR	0.4336	0.4591	0.4924	0.4296	0.4332	0.4355	0.4040	0.4131	0.4224
BGCN	0.6474	0.8245	0.9192	0.4587	0.4787	0.4846	0.3451	0.3821	0.3878
BRUCE	0.8813	0.9566	0.9811	0.7141	0.7230	0.7239	0.7410	0.7701	0.7770